

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Sustainability rating methodology

Deliverable 5.9

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the refined Sustainability Rating Method (SRM) developed under the TransformAr project and introduces an operational Excel-based assessment tool designed for practical application across diverse adaptation contexts. Building on the sustainability profiles of validated solutions and region-specific portfolios (RSPs) developed in D5.2 - Sustainability profiles of solutions, this deliverable translates the method into a user-oriented tool that enables structured, transparent, and replicable sustainability assessments.

The SRM offers a systematic and objective framework to evaluate the environmental, economic and social dimensions of sustainability. It is specifically tailored to the five categories of Actionable Adaptation Solutions (AAS) that were identified, tested, and validated within the TransformAr project: Behavioral Change and Awareness-Raising (BCAR), Governance Schemes (GS), Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), Technological and Digital Solutions (TDS), and Insurance, Financial, and Economic Instruments (IFE). The SRM integrates both qualitative and quantitative data and links indicator-level performance to relevant Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) targets. It supports comparative assessment across different solution types and operational contexts, making it easier for stakeholders to evaluate sustainability impacts and adoption potential. While the detailed development and application of the methodology were presented in D5.2, this deliverable summarizes its key components and focuses on guiding users in applying the Excel-based tool*. The goal is to facilitate continued use and transferability of the method across regions and institutions, enabling informed, transparent, and SDG-aligned sustainability assessments for future climate adaptation planning.

D5.9 operationalizes the SRM through a digital tool and accompanying instructions that allow future users - particularly Technical Support Partners and local stakeholders - to apply the method consistently and flexibly based on the needs and expectations of their cities, communities, or regions. The Excel-based tool supports indicator selection, data scoring, SDG alignment, and automated visualization, thereby streamlining the process of developing sustainability profiles.

While D5.2 focused on validating the methodology through demonstrator-specific profiles, D5.9 provides the methodological interface and guidance for its broader use. It represents a crucial step toward the transfer and upscaling of the SRM, empowering stakeholders to conduct integrated and adaptive sustainability assessments that inform decision-making and policy design. This deliverable also lays the foundation for the demonstrator-specific final assessments to be reported in D5.7 - Ex-post assessment of the solution - and further supports the continuity of the methodology in future applications.

* Excel-based tool can be downloaded from here: “D5.9 - Sustainability rating methodology (linked tool)” from [10.5281/zenodo.17638024](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17638024).

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AAS	Actionable adaptive solutions
AF	Adaptation Fund
AI	Artificial intelligence
AWAR	Awareness-raising modules
BNG	Biodiversity Net Gain
CAE	Citizen app Egaleo
CAF	Citizen App Finland
CEI	Choice experiment
CCA	Climate change adaptation
CC	Climate Change
CIH	Climate innovation hub
COAST	Coastal Contract
DSI	Demand analysis for social services and infrastructures
GB	Green bonds
HT	Handprint thinking
ICW	Integrated Constructed Wetlands
ICWM	Integrated Constructed Wetlands Monitoring
INTERM	Intertidal Monitoring
KCS	Key community system
LCT	Life cycle thinking
MRM	Mussel Raft Monitoring
NBS	Nature-based solution
NUDG	Nudging
RA	Risk assessment
RI	Resilience Index
SCS	Smart Climate Stations
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SG	Smart gate
SRM	Sustainability rating method
SWMM	Stormwater monitoring
URB	Nature-based urban stormwater solution

TA	Transformational adaptation
TSP	Technical Support Partners
WRT	Westcountry Rivers Trust

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Transformational climate adaptation requires structured, transparent, and context-sensitive approaches to evaluate the effectiveness, sustainability, and scalability of adaptation solutions. Within the TransformAr project, the Sustainability Rating Method (SRM) was developed as a response to this need. The method provides a systematic and objective framework for assessing the sustainability impacts and profiles of Actionable Adaptation Solutions (AAS) tested across six diverse European demonstrator regions.

Deliverable 5.2 (Sustainability Profiles of Solutions) introduced the SRM and applied it to evaluate 19 validated solutions and six region-specific portfolios (RSPs). These solutions span five adaptation domains: Behavioural Change and Awareness-Raising (BCAR), Governance Schemes (GS), Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), Technological and Digital Solutions (TDS), and Insurance, Financial and Economic Instruments (IFE). D5.2 detailed the methodological foundation and provided extensive sustainability assessments for each solution and demonstrator portfolio, based on qualitative and quantitative indicators aligned with relevant Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Deliverable 5.9 builds on this foundation by refining the methodology and translating it into a user-friendly Excel-based assessment tool. This tool facilitates consistent application of the SRM by stakeholders, enabling broader transfer and adoption beyond the original demonstrators. By digitizing the method and providing structured guidance, D5.9 enhances the usability, transparency, and replicability of sustainability assessments in future adaptation contexts.

1.2 Objectives and scope

The objective of Deliverable 5.9 is to operationalize the SRM as a practical tool for use by technical partners, public institutions, and local stakeholders engaged in climate adaptation. This includes:

- Refining the SRM methodology to support consistent and objective assessments of solution performance across the environmental, social, and economic dimensions of sustainability;
- Providing an Excel-based assessment tool that facilitates the scoring, SDG alignment, aggregation, and visualization of indicator data;
- Offering clear and actionable guidance for using the tool, based on the methodological steps and performance categories introduced in D5.2;
- Supporting the transferability and scaling of the method to new regions, cities, and institutions facing diverse climate risks and socio-economic conditions.

The SRM is not intended as a universal sustainability tool for all adaptation or mitigation solutions. Instead, it has been specifically tailored to assess the types of solutions implemented and validated within the TransformAr project. These include 19 Actionable Adaptation Solutions (AAS) with demonstrated impact and contextual relevance across six demonstrator regions. These solutions are detailed in Deliverable 5.2 and in Section 3.0.

By focusing on these validated solutions, the SRM remains both structured and adaptable. Its design enables application across diverse implementation environments while maintaining clarity and consistency. The tool supports individual solution assessments with built-in flexibility to accommodate varying levels of data availability and local stakeholder input.

Deliverable 5.9 serves as a practical bridge between the in-depth methodological framework developed in D5.2 and the upcoming assessment guide to be presented in Deliverable 5.7 (Ex-post Assessment of

Solutions). This ensures methodological continuity, supports replication and scaling, and strengthens coherence across Work Package 5.

1.3 Target audiences

The SRM tool and this deliverable are intended to serve a broad range of stakeholders involved in the design, implementation, assessment, and scaling of transformational adaptation actions. Target audiences include:

1. Technical Support Partners and Project Developers

Organizations supporting cities and regions in planning and implementing adaptation measures can use the SRM tool to evaluate sustainability impacts, support decision-making, and justify solution selection. The tool enables a structured approach for comparing alternatives, identifying risks, and optimizing sustainability performance.

2. Local and Regional Authorities

Municipal governments, regional administrations, and public utilities can apply the SRM to assess the long-term value of proposed or implemented solutions. By linking performance indicators to SDGs and integrating local data, the tool helps align adaptation strategies with sustainability goals, policy priorities, and stakeholder expectations.

3. Researchers and Practitioners

Universities, think tanks, and consultants working on climate adaptation, sustainability assessments, or SDG localization may use the SRM to support integrated evaluation of adaptation measures. The methodological transparency and SDG mapping functions are especially relevant for research, monitoring, and reporting purposes.

4. Community Stakeholders and NGOs

Civil society actors participating in adaptation projects can use the results generated by the SRM tool to improve understanding of solution performance, ensure inclusivity, and advocate for sustainability and resilience-oriented policies at the local level.

By supporting a wide range of users, the SRM tool promotes a shared understanding of sustainability impacts, encourages transparency in adaptation planning, and facilitates meaningful stakeholder engagement in transformational change processes.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

This section provides a summary of the SRM as developed and applied in D5.2 and explains how it is operationalized in this document through a structured, Excel-based tool. The methodology remains consistent with the original framework and is now designed to be accessible and applicable for diverse users evaluating validated climate adaptation solutions within the TransformAr project.

2.1 Assessment framework

The sustainability assessment framework builds upon the foundational definition from the Brundtland Commission (Brundtland, 1987) “meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”. The three interconnected pillars— environmental, economic, and social dimensions - frequently depicted through Venn diagrams, concentric circles, or structural metaphors—form the basis of sustainable development (Giddings et al., 2002), (Lozano, 2008; Purvis et al., 2019). The framework aligns closely with the UN’s Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which offer a globally accepted roadmap for achieving sustainability by addressing poverty, environmental degradation, and economic inequality (Emas, 2015; Taylor, 2016).

Although the SDGs provide a robust global agenda, their direct application to local sustainability assessments can be limited. Therefore, the framework incorporates Societal Relations to Nature (SRN) as a theoretical foundation to strengthen the holistic understanding of sustainability (Becker et al., 2011; Görg, 2011; Hummel et al., 2017). Drawing from D5.2 Sustainability Profiles of Solutions, the framework applies a structured linkage between specific SDGs, sub-goals, and sustainability indicators, organizing them under three domains: social (e.g., SDG1-5 & 11), economic (e.g., SDG6-10, 12, 16 & 17), and ecological (e.g., SDG13-15). These domains guide performance evaluations of adaptive solutions by linking measurable impacts with globally standardized goals, enabling consistent and context-aware assessments.

Figure 2.1 Sustainability assessment framework and relational entities, aspects, and assigned SDGs

2.2 Implementation approaches

The implementation of the SRM operationalizes the sustainability assessment framework by integrating Life Cycle Thinking (LCT), Handprint Thinking (HT), and Risk Assessment (RA) - together providing a balanced, comprehensive, and context-sensitive evaluation of solutions.

Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) is an approach that evaluates the environmental, social, and economic impacts of a product or service throughout its entire life cycle—from raw material extraction to production, use, and disposal. This holistic perspective helps identify opportunities to improve sustainability performance at each stage of the product's life (de Fátima Maciel et al., 2024). By considering the full life cycle, LCT ensures that sustainability assessments capture all relevant impacts, avoiding the shifting of burdens from one stage to another.

Handprint thinking (HT) focuses on the positive impacts that actions can have on sustainability. It encourages proactive measures to create beneficial outcomes, complementing the traditional focus on reducing negative impacts. HT emphasizes the importance of actions that contribute positively to social and environmental well-being. This approach helps in identifying and promoting practices that generate positive sustainability impacts, thereby enhancing the overall sustainability profile of solutions (Husgafvel, 2023).

Together, LCT and HT provide a dual perspective: LCT highlights where harm can be minimized, and HT identifies how benefits can be maximized. This integrated approach offers a robust foundation for holistic sustainability assessment and informed decision-making.

The SRM is implemented through a structured process that begins with the definition of context-specific criteria, indicators, and system boundaries for each demonstrator. This foundation is risk-based, **with Risk Assessment (RA)** embedded in participatory stakeholder interviews. In these interviews, stakeholders were asked targeted questions to surface perceived vulnerabilities, local challenges, and potential barriers, which directly informed the identification of context-relevant risks and the selection of appropriate indicators.

The process is supported by multiple data sources - project monitoring reports, modelling outputs, and experimental field data - ensuring systematic, transparent, and ethical evaluation. By combining robust evidence with participatory insights, the SRM enables a performance-driven assessment that captures the complexity of real-world implementation and supports continuous improvement toward long-term sustainability impact (see Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2 Sustainability rating method implementation

2.3 Process and steps

To support practical application, the SRM has been structured into a set of clear methodological steps for implementation (see Figure 2.3). These steps are grouped into four distinct phases: Scoping, Implementation, Data Process, and Assessment. Each phase includes specific tasks that guide users through the sustainability evaluation process - from defining local priorities and selecting indicators, to collecting and scoring data, and finally interpreting results for strategic decision-making.

A preliminary version of this process was introduced in Deliverable D5.2 to support structured assessments within each TransformAr demonstrator. In D5.9, this guide has been refined, operationalized, and integrated into an Excel-based tool that enables step-by-step application of the method. Feedback and practical insights from the demonstrators have helped shape the usability of this tool, making the SRM process more transparent, replicable, and adaptable across varied operating environments.

Figure 2.3 Phases and steps of sustainability rating method

The **Scoping** phase establishes the foundation for assessment. It involves identifying region-specific climate and socio-economic challenges, setting strategic adaptation objectives, defining a baseline, and selecting tailored Actionable Adaptation Solutions (AAS). These steps ensure that assessments are context-sensitive and goal-oriented.

The **Implementation** phase evaluates the performance of selected solutions using Life Cycle Thinking (LCT), Handprint Thinking (HT), and Risk Assessment (RA). Stakeholders collaboratively define performance indicators aligned with SDG targets, tailored to the local context and sustainability priorities.

In the **Data Process** phase, users gather evidence from monitoring reports, field studies, modelling, interviews, and other sources. This data is then normalized to produce indicator scores, which are subsequently weighted and aggregated to construct a comprehensive sustainability profile.

The final **Assessment** phase involves interpreting the results, managing uncertainties, and establishing mechanisms for tracking and continuous improvement. This phase ensures that the solutions are adaptable, scalable, and contribute meaningfully to long-term sustainability goals.

Table 2.1 summarizes the phases and key steps of the SRM, providing a practical reference for users applying the Excel-based assessment tool.

Table 2.1 Description of the steps in sustainability rating method

Phase	Step	Description
Scoping	1	Challenges Identify climate risks and socio-economic challenges per demonstrator using both short- and long-term perspectives.
	2	Objectives Define strategic goals that guide adaptive planning - such as risk reduction, resilience building, and sustainability enhancement.
	3	Baseline Assess current conditions using qualitative and quantitative data as a reference for future progress.
	4	Solutions Select tailored Actionable Adaptation Solutions (AAS) based on needs, capacities, and local conditions.
Implementation	5	Performance Assess environmental, social, and economic performance of selected solutions using LCT, HT, and RA.
	6	Indicators Co-develop relevant and risk-based indicators with stakeholders to reflect local context and strategic goals.
Data Process	7	Gather Data Collect data from monitoring reports, field data, modeling, interviews and secondary sources.
	8	Assign Scores Score qualitative indicators using a 0–5 scale based on progress from baseline to target
	9	Normalize, Weight and Aggregate Normalize quantitative indicators to produce their scores. Then apply weights to all indicators, and aggregate scores by SDG to generate a sustainability profile.
Assessment	10	Interpretation Analyze results to identify performance trends, gaps, and SDG contributions; support strategic action.
	11	Uncertainties Identify and manage data quality issues, overlapping indicators, and methodological challenges.
	12	Track & Improvement Enable continuous monitoring and iterative refinement of solutions and indicators to support long-term impact.

3.0 SOLUTION OVERVIEW

A total of 19 Actionable Adaptation Solutions (AAS) served as the foundation for initiating the sustainability assessment process within the TransformAr project. These solutions were implemented across six demonstrator regions, each designed to address specific local challenges arising from climate change impacts, such as water-related risks, ecosystem degradation, and socio-economic vulnerability. Collectively, they provide the practical basis for applying and validating the SRM.

To enable a structured, comparable, and context-sensitive evaluation, the 19 solutions were organized into five distinct categories based on their core adaptation strategies and implementation modalities:

- Behavioural Change and Awareness-Raising (BCAR)
- Governance Schemes (GS)
- Nature-Based Solutions (NBS)
- Technological and Digital Solutions (TDS)
- Insurance, Financial, and Economic Instruments (IFE)

This categorization supports a targeted assessment approach, allowing performance indicators, sustainability dimensions, and risk profiles to be tailored according to the specific characteristics of each solution type. It also facilitates cross-comparison, replication, and aggregation of results across the TransformAr demonstrators.

This section offers a brief overview of the five AAS categories, where full solution profiles and sustainability performance results are detailed in Deliverable D5.2. The Scoping worksheet in the D5.9 Excel tool provides direct access to categorized solutions for practical assessment using the SRM.

3.1 Behavioural Change and Awareness-Raising

Behavioural Change and Awareness-Raising Solutions (BCAR) aim to promote climate awareness, sustainable practices, and community resilience. Four such solutions were implemented in TransformAr. Effective behavioural design depends on timely, context-specific interventions that engage individuals and communities in meaningful ways to encourage lasting changes in attitudes and daily practices.

Table 3.1 Behavioural Change and Awareness-Raising Solutions

Solution name	Acronym	Description	Demonstrator
Nudging	NUDG	A behavioral intervention targeting tourists, using flyers, stickers, and shower sensors to raise awareness of water use and gently encourage reduced consumption in hotels.	Guadeloupe, France
Citizen App Egaleo	CAE	Citizen app enabling residents to engage in climate dialogue, access local microclimate data, and provide feedback, supporting participatory governance and climate awareness.	Egaleo, Greece
Awareness-raising modules	AWAR	Awareness-raising programme targeting 16–18-year-old youth to enhance climate literacy and civic engagement through participatory training, school-based modules, and creative learning strategies fostering long-term behavioural change.	Egaleo, Greece

Citizen App Finland	CAF	A crowd-sensing and real-time monitoring platform designed to enhance public awareness of climate change and urban stormwater management.	Lappeenranta, Finland
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3.2 Governance schemes

Governance schemes (GS) in TransformAr address institutional challenges in climate adaptation by promoting inclusive, cross-sector collaboration. Four solutions were implemented to empower local actors, improve coordination, and build trust. Effective governance requires trusted change agents to unite stakeholders, interpret complex information, and drive action at regional and local levels.

Table 3.2 Governance Schemes

Solution name	Acronym	Description	Demonstrator
Demand analysis for social services / infrastructure	DSI	Demand analysis for social services and infrastructure to understand how demand for social services may shift as the impacts of climate change are felt.	Egaleo, Greece
Climate Innovation Hub	CIH	Physical meeting space exhibiting solutions to climate change adaptation and offering a space for collaboration, raising awareness and events such as hackathons and Green Open Days.	Egaleo, Greece
Resilience Index	RI	Comprehensive assessment of climate adaptation needs for the mussel aquaculture sector, using modelling to input information about risks, climate change scenarios, etc., to give valuable insights helping decision makers in both the productive and political sectors to make informed decisions about governance and policy formulation.	Galicia, Spain
Coastal Contracts	COAST	Managing coastal wetlands more effectively by overcoming the fragmentation of local governance through collaborative decision-making and centralised climate data monitoring.	Oristano, Italy

3.3 Nature-based solutions

Nature-based solutions (NBS) harness natural ecosystem processes to tackle environmental, social, and economic challenges. In TransformAr, several NBS were implemented to demonstrate their effectiveness in improving climate resilience. NBS are increasingly recognized for their role in managing water and nutrients, supporting biodiversity, reducing flood risks, and delivering co-benefits for communities and ecosystems alike.

Table 3.3 Nature-Based Solutions

Solution name	Acronym	Description	Demonstrator
Smart Gates	SG	A precision water flow control system supporting wetland restoration to improve water quality, flood resilience, and ecosystem health, offering a scalable model for adaptive management.	Oristano, Italy
Integrated constructed wetlands	ICW	Nature-based solutions such as riparian buffers, floodplain wetlands, and ponds to capture sediment, reduce nutrient loading in rivers, and	West-Country Region, UK

		enhance water storage and riparian habitats in key catchments.	
Nature-based urban stormwater solution	URB	A biofiltration system that captures and treats urban runoff using vegetation and sensors, reducing flood risks, improving water quality, and supporting ecosystem resilience in urban settings.	Lappeenranta, Finland

3.4 Technological and digital solutions

Technological and digital solutions (TDS) support the acceleration and scaling of transformational adaptation. Within the TransformAr project, several innovative digital solutions were demonstrated, including IoT sensors and real-time monitoring. These tools enhance responsiveness to climate impacts, improve decision-making, and can reduce emissions by enabling smarter, more efficient adaptation strategies across sectors.

Table 3.4 Digital & Technological Solutions

Solution name	Acronym	Description	Demonstrator
Smart Climate Stations	SCS	Municipal climate monitoring stations that provide real-time microclimate data, supporting urban planning, risk assessment, and adaptive decision-making for climate-resilient infrastructure and community safety.	Egaleo, Greece
Mussel-Raft Monitoring	MRM	Deploying IoT-powered, solar-supported sensors on mussel rafts to collect real-time marine data, improving aquaculture management, environmental monitoring, and climate resilience through collaborative, adaptive decision-making.	Galicia, Spain
Intertidal Monitoring	INTERM	A monitoring approach combining seasonal sediment sampling, topographic and bathymetric surveys, and short-term sensor deployments to track sediment dynamics and environmental conditions, supporting risk assessment and protection of shellfish habitats.	Galicia, Spain
Stormwater Monitoring	SWMM	A scalable digital platform that collects and analyses data from real-time sensors installed within the biofiltration area, urban drainage systems, and other strategic locations across the city.	Lappeenranta, Finland
Integrated Constructed Wetlands Monitoring	ICWM	Monitoring water quality and biodiversity using citizen science and professional tools in nature-based solutions like riparian buffers and floodplain wetlands.	West Country Region, UK

3.5 Insurance, financial, and economic schemes

Insurance, financial, and economic schemes (IFE) are essential for scaling climate adaptation at local and regional levels. In TransformAr, various financing mechanisms were tested to support investment in adaptation solutions, reduce risks, and enable long-term implementation through tailored, context-specific approaches that align with local governance, economic capacity, and climate priorities.

Table 3.5 Insurance Schemes and Financial Solutions

Solution name	Acronym	Description	Demonstrator
Adaptation Fund	AF	A hybrid financing mechanism supporting governance, nature-based, technological, and behavioural solutions to climate risks, enhancing flexibility, local ownership, and coordinated investment for resilience.	Guadeloupe, France
Choice experiment	CEI	A survey-based tool using discrete choice experiment to understand citizens' willingness to pay for and act on stormwater management on their own properties, providing insight to the segments of the population who are willing to pay for nature-based solutions and the trade-offs they are willing to make.	Lappeenranta, Finland and Gjøvik, Norway
Green Bonds	GB	Phosphate credits to allow housing developers to fund ecosystem services and compensate landowners who set aside agricultural land to ensure long-term sustainable development in the catchment.	West Country Region, UK

4.0 HOW TO USE

The Excel tool provided in this deliverable is designed to guide users through the structured evaluation and rating of sustainability solutions using the SRM. It follows a step-by-step process, beginning with the initial scoping of solutions and concluding with the assessment of sustainability performance. The tool is organized across several interlinked sheets, each supporting a key phase of the rating method.

All worksheets in the Excel tool begin with a clearly defined **Instruction box** at the top of the sheet. These boxes provide essential guidance for each phase of the SRM. Guidance marked with 📌 indicates concrete steps that users should follow within the tool to ensure a smooth and consistent workflow across all phases.

4.1 Sheet Introduction

The '**Introduction**' sheet outlines the purpose of the tool and summarizes the overall workflow. It provides brief guidance to help users understand how the different sheets are connected and includes references to additional sources for more detailed information on the method.

The Excel tool is structured to follow the **four phases** of the SRM, with each main sheet corresponding to a specific **Phase (P)** in the methodology in Figure 4.1. This structure ensures a logical and traceable workflow from initial scoping to final assessment.

This Excel tool includes five sheets covering the four phases, each with step-by-step guidance provided in the Instruction Box on every sheet.

P1: Scoping	In this first step, users define the adaptation context by analyzing climate challenges, setting objectives, establishing baseline conditions, and identifying actionable solutions, guided by the Adaptive Pathway Transformation Playbook and supporting tools.
P2: Implementation	This step focuses on co-defining performance categories and relevant sustainability indicators to assess the selected solution across environmental, economic, and social dimensions, ensuring alignment with SDGs and measurable impact.
P3.A_Score Assignment	In this step, users assign scores to indicators by collecting local data, reviewing indicator rationale and types, and entering values to evaluate solution performance across baseline, target, and current states.
P3.B_Weighted Aggregation	In this step, users assess the importance of each indicator and performance category by assigning weights, enabling a weighted aggregation of scores to reflect the solution's overall sustainability performance.
P4.Assessment	This step presents the solution's sustainability profile by mapping indicators to SDGs, visualizing performance gaps, and enabling users to track progress and refine inputs based on local context and objectives.
Database	⚠️ The "Database" sheet contains all reference data essential for the tool's calculations. It should only be modified by an Admin, as unauthorized changes may compromise the accuracy of the results.

Figure 4.1 Introduction of worksheets

📌 The "P" in each sheet name stands for Phase, directly linking each part of the tool to the structured sequence of the SRM process. This naming convention helps users follow the method step-by-step, with clear alignment to each phase's goals and outputs.

4.2 Worksheet P1.Scoping

This worksheet begins with a clear **Instruction box** (Figure 4.2) that guides users through the key steps of Phase 1 in the SRM. In this initial phase, users define the adaptation context through four key steps:

1. Analyze climate-related challenges
2. Identify the objectives that the planned actions should address
3. Define the baseline conditions that set the reference point for evaluation
4. Identify the actionable adaptive solutions (AAS) to be implemented

Instruction box

In this initial phase, users define the adaptation context through 4 key steps: 1) Analyse the climate-related challenges; 2) Identify the objectives the actions should target; 3) Define the baseline conditions; 4) Identify the actionable adaptive solutions (AAS) to be implemented.

 This process can be supported by the [Adaptive Pathway Transformation Playbook](#).

 Tools on the [Avoided Damages and Benefits](#) can also be explored to support the process.

The Technical Manual provides descriptions and illustrations of all the elements included in this SRM tool.

The following table presents the climate risks, key community systems (KCS), and the actionable adaptive solutions (AAS) implemented in the TransformAr project. It serves as a reference to support the identification and application of suitable adaptation solutions across diverse contexts.

Figure 4.2 Introduction box

 This process is best supported by the [Adaptive Pathway Transformation Playbook](#), which offers structured guidance for identifying and sequencing adaptation pathways.

 Users may also explore tools focused on [Avoided Damages and Benefits](#) to enrich the context analysis.

A reference table is included in this worksheet showing the **climate risks, key community systems (KCS), and actionable adaptive solutions (AAS)** implemented in the TransformAr project. This supports users in identifying suitable adaptation options tailored to diverse local contexts.

 Please note: While this step provides foundational context, detailed analysis of risks and adaptation pathways is not the focus of this Excel tool. Users are encouraged to follow the suggested supporting tools and materials via the clickable links embedded in the worksheet for deeper exploration.

4.3 Worksheet P2.Implementation

The goal of this phase is to identify the relevant performance categories and indicators for assessing the selected adaptive solution. It involves two main steps:

1. Conduct a comprehensive evaluation of the solution's expected performance across the environmental, economic, and social dimensions.
2. Select appropriate sustainability indicators - both quantitative and qualitative - based on their relevance, measurability, and sensitivity to change.

This is a co-creation process, involving interviews and collaborative discussions with demonstrators and Technical Support Partners (TSPs), through which performance categories and indicators are jointly selected to reflect local priorities and the specific characteristics of each solution. Each selected performance category is connected to a set of indicators, which are further linked to relevant Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

 Begin by **selecting the solution** you would like to assess from the dropdown menu (see an example in Figure 4.3). Once selected, the tool will automatically display the corresponding solution description and the associated performance categories linked to it.

 Under each performance category, there is a list of indicators, which you will explore and score in the next worksheet (P3.A_Score Assignment).

 All subsequent steps in the tool are automatically linked to the solution chosen in this phase, ensuring consistency throughout the assessment process.

Please select the solution:	RI
Name	Resilience Index
Category	Governance schemes (GS)
Description	Comprehensive assessment of climate adaptation needs for the mussel aquaculture sector, using modelling to input information about risks, climate change scenarios, etc., to give valuable insights helping decision makers in both the productive and political sectors to make informed decisions about governance and policy formulation

Performance categories	Description
Stakeholder Engagement and Participation	This category is framed as a key social dimension that ensures inclusivity, co-creation, and shared ownership of adaptive solutions. Its purpose is to capture how effectively stakeholders—including citizens, institutions, private entities, and civil society—are engaged across the different stages of solution design, implementation, and evaluation.
Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	This category is designed to assess how effectively solutions are tracked, evaluated, and adapted over time to ensure their relevance, effectiveness, and scalability.
Management and Coordination	This category evaluates the effectiveness and sustainability of operational and organizational processes that support the implementation of adaptation solutions.
Financial Viability	This category refers broadly to the economic sustainability and cost-effectiveness of implementing solutions. It focuses on ensuring that financial resources are used efficiently and that the long-term financial sustainability of the solutions is achievable.
Risk and Resilience	This category evaluates the extent to which a solution enhances a system's ability to anticipate, absorb, adapt to, and recover from climate-related hazards such as floods. It reflects the robustness and flexibility of both physical and institutional infrastructures to manage present and future risks. Solutions scored under this category are assessed based on their contribution to reducing vulnerabilities, enhancing preparedness, and strengthening adaptive capacity across different socio-economic and environmental domains.

Figure 4.3 Selection of the solution (example shows the selection of the solution “RI”)

4.4 Worksheet P3.A_Score Assignment

The purpose of this step is to **assign scores** to the selected solution based on the sustainability indicators identified under each performance category (P2.Implementation). The tool automatically displays the relevant performance categories and their associated indicators based on your earlier selection. Some indicators include sub-indicators for a more detailed evaluation. While quantitative data is preferred, it is often challenging to obtain, particularly for pilot solutions where clear baselines or targets may not yet exist. In such cases, qualitative indicators are used, drawing on evidence, experience, and the best available knowledge provided by the demonstrator or Technical Support Partners (TSPs).

Each indicator or sub-indicator is accompanied by:

- A clear Rationale and Calculation method
- Its Measurement type (quantitative or qualitative)
- A Type tag: HIB – Higher Is Better, LIB – Lower Is Better, Q – Qualitative
- Unit of each indicator

The worksheet also displays Reference data for the current demonstrator, including:

- Baseline (initial state)
- Target (desired state)
- AAS (present state)
- The associated Score

 Begin by gathering relevant data from trusted sources such as existing databases, surveys, field studies, or expert consultations. This helps ensure a comprehensive and locally informed evaluation of the current state. **Input your localized data** in the **User input** columns where applicable (Figure 4.4,

highlighted in Yellow). The tool will automatically calculate and normalize the score according to the indicator's type and direction.

 This worksheet is where scoring begins - but it builds entirely on the structure set in the previous phase. The accuracy and completeness of scoring depend on high-quality, context-specific data and a clear understanding of each indicator's intent.

Solution selected	RI
Performance categories	Stakeholder Engagement and Participation
	Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation
	Management and Coordination
	Financial Viability
	Risk and Resilience

Performance category	Indicator	Measurement	Type	Unit	Reference				User input			
					Baseline	Target	AAS	Score	Baseline	Target	AAS	Score
Stakeholder Engagement and Participation	Workshop Attendance	Quantitative	HIB	Number of attendees	0,0	36,0	28,0	3,9				
Stakeholder Engagement and Participation	Stakeholders Participation	Quantitative	HIB	Number of stakeholders	0,0	40,0	33,0	4,1				
Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Knowledge Outputs	Quantitative	HIB	Number of new correlations	0,0	2,0	5,0	5,0				
Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Decision Tool Perception Improvement	Quantitative	HIB	Number of outputs	0,0	3,0	2,0	3,3				

Figure 4.4 User inputs for each indicator

4.5 Worksheet P3.B_Weighted Aggregation

In this step, users evaluate the relative importance of each indicator and performance category in assessing the sustainability of the selected solution. This is done by assigning the importance level of the parameter, which is automatically converted into **weighting factors** that are then used to aggregate the normalized scores from the previous step (P3.A_Score Assignment) into an overall performance score.

The data in this worksheet is automatically linked to the selections and scores provided earlier. Additionally, reference data and example results from the current demonstrator are displayed to support decision-making.

 Input your values in the **User Input → Importance (1–5)** columns (Figure 4.5). Based on the inputs from the previous step, the cells where you need to enter Importance values will be automatically highlighted in Yellow.

Solution selected:		RI									
Performance category	Indicator	User input									SDGs allocation
		Indicator/Sub-indicator		Indicator			Performance				
		Score	Weighting	Score	Importance (1-5)	Weighting	Score	Importance (1-5)	Weighting		
Stakeholder Engagement and Participat	Workshop Attendance	3,89	100 %	3,89	4,0	44 %	4,02	5,0	28 %	4,16	
Stakeholder Engagement and Participat	Stakeholders Participation	4,13	100 %	4,13	5,0	56 %				9,13	
Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Knowledge Outputs	5,00	100 %	5,00	4,0	14 %	4,58	5,0	28 %	9,13	
Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Decision Tool Perception Improve	3,33	100 %	3,33	4,0	14 %				9,13	
Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Stakeholder Collaboration Impac	4,00	100 %	4,00	4,0	14 %				9,13,17	
Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Decision-Making Tool Perception	4,64	100 %	4,64	3,0	11 %				9,13	
Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Resilience Enhancement Actions d	5,00	100 %	5,00	4,0	14 %				13,16	
Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Stakeholder Groups Diversity	5,00	100 %	5,00	4,0	14 %				9,13	
Monitoring, Evaluation, and Adaptation	Delphi Consultation Effectiveness	5,00	100 %	5,00	5,0	18 %				9,13	
Management and Coordination	Institutional Coordination	3,00	100 %	3,00	5,0	33 %	3,67	4,0	22 %	16,17	
Management and Coordination	Communication Strategy Readine	4,00	100 %	4,00	4,0	27 %				9,13	
Management and Coordination	Expertise Identification	4,00	100 %	4,00	3,0	20 %				9,16	
Management and Coordination	Stakeholder Experts Identification	4,00	100 %	4,00	3,0	20 %				9,16	
Financial Viability	Investment	5,00	50 %	4,50	3,0	100 %	4,50	4,0	22 %	8,9,13	

Figure 4.5 User inputs for importance of indicator and performance categories

When assigning importance level values, keep in mind the guiding prompt questions (?) provided below to support your decision-making.

For Indicators:

? ✓ Within each performance category, how important is this indicator in capturing the sustainability of the solution?

👉 Assign an **importance level from 1 to 5** for each indicator:

- 1 – Slightly Important
- 2 – Moderately Important
- 3 – Important
- 4 – Very Important
- 5 – Critically Important

The tool will automatically calculate relative weights, ensuring that the sum of indicator weights within each performance category equals 100%.

For Performance Categories:

? ✓ How important is each performance category in evaluating the overall sustainability of your solution?

👉 Assign an **importance level from 1 to 5** for each performance category:

- 1 – Slightly Important
- 2 – Moderately Important
- 3 – Important
- 4 – Very Important
- 5 – Critically Important

The tool will automatically calculate relative category weights, ensuring the total weight across all performance categories equals 100%.

📄 Carefully consider local priorities and solution goals when assigning importance levels. These weightings directly influence the aggregated results and final sustainability profile.

4.6 Worksheet P4.Assessment

In this step, the sustainability profile of the selected solution is presented, showing how its performance aligns with the SDGs and broader sustainability domains, based on the assessed indicators.

Each indicator is mapped to relevant SDGs by linking its measured outcome to appropriate SDG sub-goals. The scores of the indicators assigned to each sub-goal are then aggregated to the corresponding SDG level, allowing for a structured and consistent assessment. The results are compiled into a comprehensive overview that ensures all collected data is evaluated, standardized, and clearly communicated in line with sustainability objectives.

👉 You can choose to **view the assessment profile** using either:

- **Reference** data (from the current demonstrator), or
- **User** input, which reflects local conditions and custom scores provided in earlier steps.

A dynamic radar chart visualizes the distance to the target for each SDG linked to the selected indicators (Figure 4.6). Alongside the visualization, you will find a general interpretation of the results, which includes the uncertainties (details in Section 5.2) identified in the assessment, and suggestions to track the solution's performance over time and revise earlier scores to reflect updated information or priorities.

Solution selected:	RI	
Sustainability Profile of Reference's RI(Resilience Index)		
Please select the assessment profile:	Reference	
Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	Scores	Sustainability
SDG 4 – Quality Education	4,02	Social
SDG 8 – Decent Work and Economic Growth	4,00	Economic
SDG 9 – Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure	4,09	Economic
SDG 16 – Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions	4,12	Economic
SDG 17 – Partnerships for the Goals	4,17	Economic
SDG 13 – Climate Action	4,09	Environmental

Figure 4.6 Sustainability profile of selected solution

📄 This final visualization reflects all previous inputs and weightings. Revisions to indicator scores or importance values will automatically update the assessment profile, making it a living tool for continuous monitoring and improvement.

4.7 Sheet Database

The Database sheet serves as the back-end engine of the SRM tool. It contains all the reference data, structured lists, scoring logic, and definitions that power the tool's dropdowns, automatic calculations, and indicator mapping across all phases.

This sheet includes:

- The full list of performance categories, indicators, and sub-indicators
- Rationale statements, measurement types, and calculation methods
- Reference baseline, target, and current (AAS) values for the current demonstrators

- Scoring formulas and interpretation logic

 Note: This sheet is not intended for direct editing by general users. Any changes here may compromise the integrity of the tool's automated processes and final outputs.

 Modifications to this sheet should only be made by administrators or tool developers with a full understanding of the data structure and dependencies within the Excel tool.

The Database sheet ensures consistency, traceability, and reliability of results throughout the tool and should be treated as the protected foundation of the SRM assessment process.

5.0 CONCLUSIONS

5.1 Summary

This document presents a refined and operational version of the Sustainability Rating Method (SRM) developed within the TransformAr project. The SRM provides a structured and adaptable approach to assess the sustainability performance of Actionable Adaptive Solutions (AAS). It supports local decision-makers, planners, and stakeholders in evaluating climate adaptation measures based on their relevance, feasibility, and impact across environmental, social, and economic dimensions, while aligning with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Central to the deliverable is an interactive Excel-based tool, designed to operationalize the SRM through a step-by-step assessment process. The tool builds upon the logic and structure presented in Deliverable 5.2 and integrates feedback and case data from TransformAr demonstrators.

The SRM process is divided into four core phases:

1. Scoping – Define the adaptation context, challenges, objectives, and candidate solutions.
2. Implementation – Select performance categories and relevant indicators aligned with SDGs.
3. Data process – Assign performance values and weights based on baseline, target, and current conditions.
4. Assessment – Aggregate scores, map to SDGs, and visualize the sustainability profile.

Each worksheet begins with an Instruction box, and actions marked with 📌 guide users step-by-step. The tool supports both reference data from the TransformAr demonstrators and user input based on local context. Scores and weights are automatically calculated, ensuring consistent evaluation across solutions. Results are displayed visually to support strategic decision-making and improvement planning.

5.2 Strengths and Limitations

The SRM tool offers several notable strengths that make it a practical and valuable resource for assessing climate adaptation solutions. Its structured, step-by-step design – supported by clearly labeled instruction boxes and dynamic data-linking across sheets – enables users to perform assessments in a transparent and consistent way. The tool balances standardization with flexibility by allowing users to input local data, adjust importance weights, and select context-relevant indicators. Moreover, its alignment with the SDGs enhances its relevance for both local action and global reporting. The inclusion of rationale descriptions, scoring logic, and automated normalization adds further clarity and ease of use, particularly for interdisciplinary teams and stakeholders who may not have prior experience with evaluation frameworks.

However, the tool also has some methodological limitations. Being Excel-based, it requires manual data handling, which can be time-consuming and may introduce user error. The scoring and weighting mechanisms, while practical, are relatively simplified and may not fully capture interdependencies between indicators. The importance values used to calculate the weighting of each indicator and performance category are subjective and can vary depending on local conditions, stakeholder priorities, and demonstration experiences. This introduces variability in results, particularly when assessments are conducted by different teams or across different contexts.

5.3 Next steps

The next steps for advancing the SRM focus on strengthening its practical application and long-term value, with a direct link to the development of Deliverable 5.7, which will guide the ex-post assessment of adaptive solutions. In this context, the SRM indicators, developed with a life cycle perspective and

through co-creation with Technical Support Partners (TSP), capture the key factors critical to the success of each solution. In D5.7, these indicators will be applied to assess the degree of resilience capacity achieved by a solution, considering the specific needs and expectations of the cities, communities, or regions involved. This phase will not only validate the use of SRM in real-world post-implementation contexts but also generate valuable feedback for its ongoing refinement and improvement.

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Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

TransformAr

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